

**A STUDY OF MANPOWER PLANNING DIVISIONS:
A CASE STUDY OF SELECTED EDUCATIONAL DIRECTORATE
IN THE WESTERN REGIONS OF GHANA**

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Abstract:

The overall objective of this research was to evaluate (determine the effectiveness) of manpower planning activities of selected educational directorates in the Western Region of Ghana. The study, basically, was a survey which entirely utilized a questionnaire to obtain field data. The sample size of 180 was drawn from a total population of 400 which comprised teaching and non-teaching staff in the districts and officers of the district directorates. Fundamentally, the study found out that the educational workers in the district were very much aware of the relevance of manpower planning as an important management function. However, there was an irregularity with the induction training and appraisal exercises. Other results showed problems relating to recruitment and poor conditions of service. The study among other things recommended that sensitization workshops be organized by GES for human resource managers in the directorates.

Keywords: manpower planning divisions, educational directorate, Ghana

1. Introduction

Those who have lived, and particularly those who have worked in educational institutions in the Third World Countries are sometimes confronted with the difficulty of implementing the simplest policy. The problem is due to the nature of manpower planning. Oyedji (2006) has observed that manpower is an essential dimension of the works of all organizations. Corroborating this observation, Mankoe (2007) added that;

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“Planning of the manpower may be likened to a person who is embarking on a journey. The traveler must know where he is, where he wants to go, and decide on how best to get there. This simple picture explains what should be done in manpower planning.” (p135)

It is logical to reason from the above exposition that it is through manpower planning that an organization derives the right number of people with the right skills, in the right place and at the right time. Of all the resources required to harness the activities of institutions, the pool of manpower is the most significant because it is human beings that will use the other resources, and the manpower planning unit is a crucial segment for any institution. The manpower is thus very paramount for the effective functioning of the organization.

Harbison (1973) is of the view that manpower constitutes the wealth of any society since the other resources like capital and natural resources are passive factors of production. He added that manpower constitutes“

“...the active agents who accumulate capital, exploit natural resources build social, economic and political organizations and carry forward national growth and development.”

Analytically, this means that an organization with a well-planned manpower division has a greater chance to achieve its overall goal with limited financial resources. Indeed, institutional growth cannot be achieved without planning the human resources. Especially in educational institutions, manpower planning is focused on obtaining the required number of people and upgrading them. It entails the proper use of the available human resources.

Mankoe (2007) notes that manpower planning in education entails assessing the human resource needs of an institution, it also entails developing enrolment projections, reviewing the overall objectives of institution within the context of its needs including organizing the inventories, enrolment projections and objectives into human resource forecast. The above functions are the work of manpower planning division.

Mankoe (2007) and Ambekar (2004) seem to suggest that in the educational sector, manpower planning is bedeviled with challenges especially in the Ghana Education Service [GES]. For example, it is on record that in the GES, planning of human resource is not only characterized by selecting the right people for the right place and time. A key factor that is rather considered is “long service”. This apparent habit contrasts the views of Graham (2005) who noted that manpower planning should entail selecting and positioning the required staff in terms of qualification and experience for the purpose of achieving the overall goal of the institution.

Here, the needs of the personnel, their education, and the appropriate number required are very vital. When this is done, one assures himself of a strong competent, effective and efficient school administration which is an essential prerequisite for educational development. But this, by contrast, is what appears to be lacking in the majority of African countries.

It is therefore not difficult to see why the administration of many schools, district and regional educational offices are bad. Most often, a relatively small number of incompetent people are put in charge of a very large number of educational workforce. The tasks are monumental and many educational officers, overwhelmed by unfulfillable responsibilities, lapse into cynical apathy. At best, they try not to let things deteriorate; otherwise, they try to do what they can with the situation. All these are highlighted by the fact that there is no proper manpower planning. There is no solid weight given to the preparation of human resources inventories, employee's projection, the supply of human resources, recruitment practices, selection, placement and induction, appraisals, retaining and awarding staff. In other instances, it appears that people are put into offices without formal orientation organized for them to learn the rudiments of the job. The question then raised is, how effective are the manpower division of educational institutions in the country?

2. Statement of the Problem

Like many educational districts in Ghana, the selected educational districts in the Western Region has their own shares of challenges confronting educational administration, indeed challenges that may, derive from apparent ineffective and inefficient manpower planning. The educational district offices have planning, statistics, inspectorate, supervision, budget, welfare and other significant units. In the budgeting division units of the district education offices, the duty is to make an estimated budget for the number of schools in the district in order to supply the various schools with the correct and requisite teaching and learning materials. The problem is that the budgeting division is apparently not able to meet the Government time schedule to present the budget. The officers sit in the offices and guess any figure instead of going out to do proper census count. The Inspectorate and the supervision divisions reportedly do not also do their work. Teachers have been left to do whatever they like. Teachers are doing buying and selling in schools instead of proper teaching and learning, signing of wrong time in the time book and many other activities.

The officers according to reports do not go to the various schools to inspect teachers work and correct their mistakes, nor do they organize in-service training for the teachers. The welfare for the teachers is also not properly taken care of. Some parents confront teachers who cane their children. All of these units are supposedly manned by a team of manpower. But in consideration of the above, a few pertinent questions are asked about the administrative challenges confronting manpower planning division in this district?

By extension, what challenges impede the preparation of human resource inventory, enrolment and employee projection, recruitment, selection, placement and induction, retention of staff, appraisal and rewards? Has the important role of planning the manpower in the district been made effective by the manpower planning division? The main problem (question) this study attempts to address is: How effective is the

manpower division of the selected educational directorate of the Western Region and what problems confront them in the discharge of their duties.

2.1 Objectives

The following are the objectives of the study.

1. To underscore the relevance of manpower planning in educational administration and management in the selected educational directorates in the Western Region.
2. To investigate the nature of manpower planning as an element of educational administration in the selected educational directorates in the Western Region.
3. Evaluate the work of the manpower planning division of the selected educational directorates in the Western Region.
4. To find out the challenges confronting manpower planning efforts in the educational directorate of the Western Region.
5. To find solutions to the challenges confronting manpower planning efforts in the educational directorate of the Western Region.

2.2 Research Questions

The research sought to answer the following questions

1. What is the basis (relevance) of manpower planning in educational administration and Management?
2. What does manpower planning activities look like in the educational Districts in the Western Region?
3. In what ways have the nature and level of manpower planning practices of the educational directorates in the Western Region impacted education delivery in the district?
4. What problems confront manpower planning division in the selected educational directorates?
5. In what ways can the challenges be overcome to help effective educational delivery in the Western Region?

3. Literature Review

3.1 General Challenges of Educational Administration

All social organizations, whether a University, College School, Hospital, textile manufacturing firm, wholesale electronic store, church or a political party require the process of administration in order to provide high-quality goods and services (Mankoe, 2007:8). In the process of administering entities, there are numerous challenges ranging from lack of financial and material resources to lack of adequate space and manpower. In relation to manpower, effective planning of the human resource is a daunting challenge.

Anamuah-Mensah (2002) observes that despite various improvements in education, there are nevertheless challenges confronting the educational system. These

challenges can be categorized into three groups. The first emanates from the educational system itself and is referred to as internal challenges. They may consist of lapses or problems confronting the system for which we may have no control. The second type of challenge is global and it hinges on those challenges that are external to the national educational system. The third is the sub-regional specific challenges for which there is some degree of control since it relates to some border issues (p.6.). A fourth and more specific challenge is the planning of the manpower which should be done effectively to achieve organizational goals.

In Ghana, specifically as it relates to the internal challenges confronting educational administration, these generally include access to education, lack of adequate resource allocation, poor quality of instruction, poor management and supervision and increase rural-urban disparity (Nti, 1975). According to Owens (1987), other challenges generally bedeviling educational administrations are under-resourcing and under-funding of vocational-technical education, the local language-English-language controversy, inadequate information planning and absence of alternative learning pathways for poor learners.

3.2 Manpower Planning in Education

All educational institution need various kinds of staffs to get them running. The truism in this is found in the assertion of Conyers (1982) who noted:

“Take away my equipment, and soon you will see new equipment in my factory. Take away my people, and soon grass will overrun the factory.” (13)

This assertion reinforces the significance of manpower in all organizations- in realizing or fulfilling the mission statement, vision goals and objectives of that organization. In education institutions, especially at the pre-tertiary level, typical examples of manpower are the headmaster/head teacher, his assistants, teachers, typists, secretaries, accounts, bursars, housemaster/mistress, matrons and various artisans like carpenters, plumbers, electricians and drivers. Others are messengers and cleaners. The activities of the pool of human resources need to be planned effectively. The recruitment, selection, placement appraisal and compensation of all manner of persons in an organization is called manpower planning. Rebores (1987) also argues that manpower planning also deals with collective negotiations between management and workers in an organization.

At the pre-tertiary level, the Ghana Education Service plays a vital role in managing personnel, while in tertiary education manpower planning rests with the registrars of Universities and secretaries of polytechnics, and in many other instances with the manpower planning divisions of these organizations.

3.3 The Importance of Manpower Planning in Education

Conyers (1982) defines planning as the rational application of human knowledge to the process of reaching decisions which are to serve as the basis for human action.

Construed as such, manpower planning assist schools to obtain the required staff needed. This observation is in line with Oyedeji (2006) who observes that manpower assists schools to make various adjustments from time to time. This connotes the fact that whether a school is focusing on human resource in Education as in other entities it is a personnel function responsible for recruiting selecting, retaining, developing and motivating employees in order to achieve optimal educational delivery. For example, Rebores (1995:8) illustrates the significance of manpower planning in the following words:

“Human resource planning as a process ensures the smooth running of a school. We consider the implications of these objectives on future demands and the future supply of human resources, and supply so as to make them compatible with the achievement of the organization’s future.”

Ambekar (2004) identifies some areas of significance in terms of manpower planning in a school system. These are:

- It is useful for both the school teachers and other personnel.
- It generates facilities to develop school personnel.
- It provides a smooth working relationship in the wake of school expansion.
- It opens the opportunity for school staff to be promoted.
- It creates a healthy school climate and makes training effective.
- It assists school staff in career development.

Very much related to Ambekar’s points are the benefits according to Oyedeji (2006) who asserts that manpower planning:

- Reduces personnel cost in view of the fact that management has the ability to anticipate shortages or surpluses of manpower and correct the imbalance.
- It provides the basis for planning employees development aimed at making optimum use of workers.
- It makes room for improvement in the overall organizational planning process.
- It provides a greater awareness of the importance of sound manpower management throughout all levels of the organization.
- It serves as a tool for evaluating the effect of manpower actions and policies.
- It helps ease the inputs of organizations and technological changes which may occur in an organization by forecasting these changes long before plans for dealing with the problems are implemented.

In the words of Boateng (2007:8), manpower planning in education is very essential since education contributes massively and directly to economic growth. Again, underscoring the role of manpower planning in education, the Ministry of Education (1995:9) states the following:

- Redesigning management structures which defines the roles and responsibilities of the Ministry of Education (MOE).
- And the GES at the headquarters, the regional and the district levels, which provides for appropriate delegation on operational matters to the district level;

- Improving mechanisms for monitoring performance at the district level and performance standards and targets for all;
- Strengthening personnel management practices which motivate individuals, groups and department throughout the systems towards achieving better performance;
- Staffing organization structures at all levels with appropriately trained and qualified managers, and
- Having adequate discretionary powers which can make a significant impact on the quality of education.

These points emphasize the significance of the human factor in the school system – especially as it relates to best practices in terms of advice and guidance. For example, manpower planning ensures consistency and fairness of treatment for all employees by gathering and processing strategies and planning.

4. Research Methodology

4.1 Research Design

The research design adopted for the study was the descriptive survey and case study. Responses were gotten from teaching and non-teaching staff of the three education offices. The researcher chose 4 main thematic areas for inquiry. These are:

- The role and relevance of manpower in educational sectors
- The nature of manpower planning, activities in the directorates
- Manpower planning practices in the directorates.
- Challenges confronting manpower planning efforts.
- Necessary actions needed to find solutions to manpower planning activities.

In carrying out the study, the descriptive survey was adopted through the use of closed-ended questionnaires. Gay (1986) describes the descriptive sample survey as involving the collection of data in order to test a hypothesis or answer research questions concerning current status (manpower planning practices in the directorates for this study). In descriptive statistics, data is gathered at a particular point in time with the intention of describing the nature of existing conditions (methods of gathering and processing of data) or identifying a standard against which existing conditions can be compared or determined the relationship that exists between specific event. The descriptive survey has been chosen for the study because of its advantage of producing responses from a wide range of people. It also provides a meaningful picture of events and seeks to explain people's opinion relating to (the nature and significance of manpower planning) the behavior on the basis of data at a particular time. Also, in-depth follow-up questions can be asked and items that are not clear can be explained using the descriptive design.

Furthermore, this method is applicable when the researcher attempts to describe aspects of the population by selecting an unbiased sample of individuals who were asked to complete questionnaires.

The study also adopted the case study design. Unlike the experimental design which manipulate variables to determine their casual significance or the survey which asks standardized questions of large representative samples of individuals, the case study researcher typically observes the characteristics of an individual unit (the manpower planning division), a child, a clique, a class, a school or a community. The purpose of such observation is to probe deeply and to analyze intensively (the evaluation of manpower planning division in the Western Region) the multifarious phenomena that constitute the life cycle of a unit with a view to establishing generalization about the wider population to which that unit belongs. (Gay, 1986)

4.2 Population and Sample Size

The population of the study consisted of all 400 teaching and non-teaching staff of the three directorates. The sample constituted the 3 district directors in the study area, twelve front line deputy directors of education, 3 accountants, 3 human resource managers, 3 girls' education coordinators in the 3 directorates, thirty circuit supervisors, 3 science and mathematics coordinators. In all 60 persons were chosen from each directorate, making a total of 180 persons for the study in terms of population

4.3 Sampling Techniques

The researchers used a purposive sampling technique to select the three district Directors of Education and their deputies. Purposive sampling technique was again used to select the other respondents except for the circuit supervisors who were chosen randomly. The three districts directorates were chosen by means of purposive sampling.

4.4 Instruments for Data Collection

The questionnaire was used to obtain data from the field. The questionnaire was used for all the respondents.

4.5 Data Collection Procedures

An introductory letter was written by the Director of the Centre for Educational Policy Studies to negotiate access to the directorates concerned. With the introductory letter, the researchers went to the schools and sought permission of the personnel to undertake the exercise of administering the questionnaires. After the letter was obtained, the researchers explained their mission and the purpose of the study to the member of the directorates. The researchers also assured the respondents of confidentiality relating to whatever information they provided and use the opportunity to explain the nature of the questionnaire. The researchers booked an appointment with the three District Directorates. All the necessary data were obtained within two weeks.

4.6 Data Analysis

The questionnaire was coded for tabulation and analyses. This provided an opportunity for checking whether respondents followed instructions uniformly and that all

questionnaires were checked as a whole rather than checking one question at a time for all questionnaires.

The method assisted in establishing possible relationships between answers to different questions and also to detect inconsistencies. The problems relating to manpower planning in the directorates were analyzed using tables and percentages

All questions were grouped under various headings and analysed one after the other. Each item in the questionnaire was treated as a separate entity and analysed independently of the other. The questions which demanded “Yes” or “No” answers were grouped and percentages calculated. The higher percentage of responses to various questionnaires was taken as adequately valid and reliable. Data collected were analysed using the percentage.

5. Results and Discussions

Research Question Number 1: What is the basis of manpower planning in educational administration and management?

A. Roles of Manpower Planning in Educational Establishments

In any organization, the manpower of that entity plays a very key role in helping the organization to achieve its objectives.

Table 1 depicts views of respondents on the relevance of manpower planning in educational institutions.

Table 1: Extent to which you think your outfit has the needed number of people relevant for the task assigned

Extent of manpower relevant	Frequency	Percentage
To a very large extent	80	44.4
To a large extent	60	33.3
To some extent	37	20.5
Not at all	3	1.6
Total	180	1000

The information in Table 1 shows an overwhelming 80(44.4%) of respondents who noted that their outfits had the needed number of people relevant for the various tasks in their respective outfits. This was followed by another group of respondents 60 (33.3%) who said to a large extent and a third category 37 (20.5%) who said to some extent. Only an insignificant number, 3 (1.6%) noted not at all. One can, therefore, deduce without any hesitation that the educational directorates in the Western Region are properly and adequately manned for the task on hand-meaning that should there be any manpower problem in the area, inadequate staff could not be the problem.

B. Relevant/Right Skills Required

In any organization, the apparent sheer number of personnel does not necessarily suggest that those who work have the right skills to do the job.

The data in Figure 1 provides information on this.

Figure 1: Do you think the People in the Office have the right skill for the job?

A vast majority 85% of respondents believed that those working in the educational offices of the Western region have the relevant skills for the tasks they perform daily. Fifteen percent (27) respondents, however, said *no*. When asked to give reasons for their answers, those that responded *yes* commented that in as much as those in the directorates were professional teachers and had first degree upwards, they were deemed qualified. On the contrary, those who said *no* argued that some teachers who had no thorough grip of administration were sent to work in the offices while others who worked in offices were sent to the classroom to teach. This could apparently lead to a skill gap.

C. The relevance of Planning the Manpower

The research sought to ascertain the views of respondents on the relevance of planning the manpower in the directorates. Data on this is shown in Table 2.

Table 2: Describe the level of the relevance of the human resource in the educational directorates

Description of relevance	Frequency	Percentage
Very relevant	86	47.7
Relevant	83	46.1
Not relevant	11	6.1
No opinion	0	0
Total	180	100

According to Table 2, most of the respondents, except 11 (6.1%) felt that it was very relevant or it was relevant to plan the human resource in the directorates. The data seems to support the view of Rebores (1987) who posits that as a result of manpower planning both management and employees can collectively negotiate a lot of issues. Thus, the fact that a combined total of 93.8% of respondents took cognisance of the relevance of manpower planning is in the right direction.

D. Need Assessment in Manpower Planning

A significant feature or requirement for any manpower planning activities is to ascertain the manpower needs of an institution through a need's assessment. Responses in Figure 2 are an indication that respondents working with various departments have undergone such exercise.

Figure 2: Has your Department Undergone any Needs Assessment Exercise?

The responses in Figure 2 demonstrate that 135 (75%) of respondents said they have had needs assessment exercises compared to 45 (25%) who said *no* it could be that either some of them were absent during needs assessment exercises or they did not grasp the actual meaning of needs assessment. What is however important is that the majority (75%) of respondents acknowledged that there were needs assessment activities in the directorates. Out of the 180 respondents, 61 (33.8%) said that the staff in the district directorate responded to the needs assessment very positively, 84 (46.6) said they responded to it positively while the rest 35 (19.4%) said the response to the need assessment exercise was just positive meaning deductively no staff had a negative attitude towards the exercise.

E. The Reaction of Personnel on the Use of Qualification in Planning in Departments

Due to the comparatively low level of literacy (education) in developing country like Ghana most often than not the use of qualification for planning and sometimes promotion often creates diverse reactions. This is especially true in the GES where in many cases there has been tension between graduate teachers and nongraduates. Table 3 presents data which represents the reaction of people to the use of qualification in manpower planning in the departments.

Table 3: Reaction of People on the use of Qualification to Plan in the Departments

Reactions	Frequencies	Percentage
Very positively	38	21.1
Positively	46	25.5
Somehow positively	60	33.3
Negatively	36	20
Total	180	100

Contrary to the assertion of Harbison (1973) that the use of qualification in departmental planning, the data in Table 3 reveals that 60 (33.3%) rather reacts somehow positively to the use of qualifications in planning in the departments. Another group of respondents 46(25.5%) reacted *positively* while the third category of respondents 38(21.1%) noted *very positively*. The lowest score, 36(20%) had their responses in the negative. A possible explanation for the way the scores were spread could be the presence of a comparatively large number of graduates in the study area at the time.

F. Areas of Manpower Planning

Manpower Planning sometimes referred to as human resource planning constitutes a wide range of activities which include but not limited to job analysis, recruitment, performance appraisal training and development, and job enrichment. The study in Table 4 sought to find out areas departments management showed greater interest in planning the human resource.

Table 4: Areas Departments Management Showed Greater Interest in Planning the Human Resource

Areas	Frequency	Percent
Preparing human resource inventory	35	19.4
Developing enrolment	47	26.1
Affirmative action	30	16.6
Staff development	30	16.6
Induction training	38	21.1
Total	180	100

The data clearly reveals that the responses are almost evenly divided among the five listed variables (categories). It was only developing enrolment projection, 47 (26.1%) which showed a very significant difference in terms of high scores. This was not really surprising because the GES directorates in Ghana are often confronted with the challenges of large class size due to large enrollment at the beginning of the academic year. Enrolment projection was followed by induction training, 38 (21.1%). This activity which is carried out for new employees is characterized by awareness creation and information sharing which ultimately leads to manpower management. The other categories, resource inventory (19.4%) affirmative action (16.6%) and staff development (16.6%) show no sharp differences in the scores.

On the issue of staff development, this often takes the form of workshop, conferences, seminars and study leave programmes.

Research Question Number 2: What does manpower planning activities look like in the education directorates in the Western Region?

Question items 15-24 were designed to solicit responses on the nature of manpower planning activities in the study area.

A. Enrolment Projection

According to Mankoe (2007:136), a school programme must make an effort to project declines or increases in the number of students. Figure 3 provides information as to whether there were enrolment projection activities in the directorates.

Figure 3: Do authorities in your district embark on enrolment projection?

The data in Figure 3 clearly show evidence of enrolment projection in the directorates. To this item 153 (85%) of respondents said *yes* as against 27(15%) who said *no*. This was very positive on the part of the directorates since the projection of enrolment say for a period of 5 to 10 years to determine retention and survival rates and general enrolment trends is a useful exercise for both the school and the community.

Further inquiries on the item to determine the frequency of enrollment projection, reveal that 98% of respondents said every year. Apparently, this was done to plan for the infrastructure and manpower (mainly teachers).

B. The extent to which the Directorates Review the Overall Objectives of Schools within the Context of Changing Staff Needs

In educational institutions, manpower planning objectives can be broken down into staffing objectives, performance objectives, change, management objectives and administrative objective. The study as indicated in Table 5 was keen to investigate the extent directorates review the overall objectives of schools within the context of changing staff needs.

Table 5: Extent to which directorates review overall objectives within the context of changing staff needs

Extent	Frequencies	Percentage
Very large extent	10	5.5
Large extent	15	8.3
Some extent	22	12.2
Not at all	132	73.3
Total	189	100

According to the data in Table 5, a vast majority 132 (73.3) of respondents responded not at all to the question item on review of objectives. Only a combined total of 47 (26.1) thought the objective of schools were under review within the context of changing staff needs. This obviously reflects a bad picture in the directorates since over time especially in the modern period, staff have changing needs which must be responded to. Ambekai (2004) seem to suggest that the human are resources to be greatly cared for and this can ultimately be done by reviewing organizational objectives within the context of the needs of the staff.

C. Forecasting Number of Staff

A fundamental practice in all functional organizations is the practice of forecasting organizational needs. This according to Wiles and Bondi (2006) will assist organization to be prepared for any eventuality. Respondents were asked to indicate ways by which their entities make a forecast in terms of staff needs.

Some of the themes that emanated as responses were:

- Submitting names of existing staff;
- Outlining future task and challenges of the entities;
- Making a comparison of male and female staff;
- Submitting a pending retirement list;
- Requesting departments to submit existing vacancies.

D. Recruitment Practices

Recruitment is a regular exercise that enables all organizations to provide efficient and effective staff who provide services for an organization. Respondents were required to describe the recruitment practices in their outfits. The responses provided are summarized as follow:

- Departmental heads and heads of schools employ staff based on the job description;
- Educational authorities recruit staff on the basis of job specification approved by the GES;
- Major tasks in the entities are determined to find the rightful skills for them;
- A determination of existing departments and future departments are made;
- Budget forecast is made to match with staff needs;
- Application forms are given out to job seekers;
- The performance test is given for various skills required;

- Information from respondents is sought.

As good as these responses are, they are by no means exhaustive since peoples interest, ability and personalities are also issued to consider. Mankoe (2007:143) noted that people’s occupational preferences and employment variables such as salaries, location and opportunities for staff development are other important variables.

E. The regularity of Placement/Induction Training

Under the broad category of staff, development is the element of placement/induction training. Responses regarding the frequencies of such training in the directorates are provided in Table 6.

Table 6: Regularity of Placement/Induction Training

Regularity	Frequencies	Percentage
Very often	15	0.8
Often	28	15.5
Very seldom	98	54.4
Not at all	39	21.6
Total	180	100

The responses represented by Table 6 shows that placement/induction training is generally a rare occasion in the directorates. This is evident by the 98 (54.4%) of respondents, whose answer was very seldom followed by another set of respondents whose answer was not at all 39 (21.6). Those whose answers were very often 15 (0.8%) and often 28 (15.5%) were comparatively insignificant perhaps the responses are depicted as such due to lack of adequate fund – an excuse and often time a real challenge existing in most public institutions. This being the case, it means that the vast majority of the staff in the directorates have not been acquainted with the activities of the school system and the relationship they must develop to be successful employees.

F. Availability of Job Appraisal Policy

Respondents were asked to indicate whether their departments/ institutions had a job appraisal policy. Figure 4 provides the statistics on this.

Figure 4: Is there any job appraisal policy in your outfit?

The responses in figure 4 reveal a dismal negative answer as indicated by 79% of respondents who said *no* as compared to 21% who said *yes*. Such responses were unexpected especially for educational organizations which are supposed to foster self-development of staff, identify different tasks which an employee is capable of performing, identify staff development needs and improve the performance of employees through appraisals (Mankoe, 2007).

G. If Yes, how does it Work?

For those (21%) who said there was such policy they indicated the following answers as to how it works

- Identifying individuals to do a valuation of specific existing jobs,
- Evaluation/appraisal of various skills of employees
- Determination of the frequencies of appraisals per annum
- Communicating results of appraisal to the appropriate agencies
- Using the results of appraisals to improve employees' skills and conditions of service

These responses though emanating from a relatively few of the respondents demonstrate that at least some departments or institutions try to create a balance in terms of expected accountability between management and staff.

H. Rewarding Good Performance

Satisfying employees' needs through various reward system are characteristic of every non-voluntary organizations. When asked how good performances were rewarded, the following answers were given:

- Promotion;
- Salary Increment;
- Praise/recognition in PTA meeting;
- Special awards during speech and prize giving days.

These responses are characteristics of what often occurs in many organizations especially those that reward not only performance but behaviours, interest and needs of the rewards.

Research Question Number 3: What problems confront manpower planning activities in the various educational directorates?

All institutions whether educational or otherwise are confronted with challenges. The following question items addressed the challenges bedeviling the various directorates.

A. Availability of Adequate Staff

Having adequate staff for various submit of entities is essential for the effective and efficient operation of those entries. Respondents were asked about the availability of enough staff in their departments. This is shown in Figure 5.

Figure 5: Does your District/Department have Enough Qualified Staff?

The data in Figure 5 shows that the district had adequate staff that manned them. It was only then expected that these staffs were in a balanced proportion in terms of gender.

Figure 5: If no then what are the challenges?

Regarding the 10% who thought the staff were not adequate, some of the challenges they provided included

- Transfer and late replacement of staff;
- Frequent retirement;
- Constant staff attrition due to a much-preferred job elsewhere.

These challenges permeate the entire structure of the GES although many educational personnel are trained every year. The Western Regional Educational directorates are therefore considered fortunate to have fewer challenges in terms of adequate staff.

B. Problems Confronting Recruitment of Qualified Staff in the District/ Departments

The need for every organization to recruit staff is very paramount. But in many cases, some entities are unable to recruit qualified staff due to a variety of challenges. When asked to list the problems confronting the recruitment of some qualified staff, the respondents variously noted the following:

- Conditions of service in the education sector were lower compared to other sectors;
- The negative image of some schools and communities;
- Lack of social amenities/support services in some school communities.

All of these constraints are particularly applicable to the GES whose employees are always agitating for better conditions of service.

Research Question Number 4: In what ways can the challenges to manpower planning be overcome for effective educational delivery in the district?

The respondents' responses were as follow:

A. Actions Needed for Staff Development Policies

- Well-coordinated programmes for staff development;

- There should be lengthy publicity on existing staff development opportunities;
- Staff development practices should be gender balanced;
- District directors should solicit more funds to encourage more staff development activities;
- Staff development should now go beyond the traditional notion of short workshops seminars and conferences. Rather, long-term programmes should be embarked upon.

B. Necessary Action for Recruitment of Qualified Staff

- Adoption of appropriate policies to help staff grow and develop. Such policies include making an adequate forecast and determining the sources of funds to complement the government's subvention;
- Avoidance of favouritism and nepotism/tribalism in recruiting staff;
- Adhering to affirmative action policies;
- Ascertaining the criminal record and certificates of applicants;
- Providing adequate incentives and conducive work environment for staff.

C. Necessary Actions Needed for Retention of Staff

- Improve the conditions of service of teachers and other educational workers
- Increase opportunities for study leave and other professional development programmes;
- Embark on comprehensive rural development;
- Enhance good leadership styles and practices of school heads and other educational officers;
- Increase fringe benefits in the educational sector. These include social security and retirement benefits.

D. Necessary Actions Needed for Induction Training

- Heads of educational units should warmly welcome new staff;
- New staff should be taught the significance of teamwork and team spirit;
- Adjustment period and activities of new staff should be adequately monitored by educational leaders;
- Adequate information on the culture of the organization and the community should be conveyed to the new staff.

An analysis of the suggested actions shows that they are very appropriate to confront manpower planning activities of the directorates in the Western region.

6. Conclusion

In conclusion, this study, it must be said that manpower planning activities in terms of performance in the directorates of the Western Region can be described as average. But if issues such as conditions of service viable work environments, appraisal policies irregular induction training and regular revision of organizational objectives in line with staff needs are not remedied, the promotion of manpower planning activities will not progress.

The ultimate basis for manpower planning activities is for the adequate management of the human resource which is the most important resource in all organizations, one which is needed for organizational excellence. Thus, apart from confronting the physical problems confronting manpower planning efforts, the GES must make sure that educational leaders are much aware and ready to conduct manpower planning activities. This will bring about greater care for the human resource in the district, maximizing employee performance, maintaining adequate data and putting in place appropriate succession plans.

6.1 Recommendations

- a) The Ghana Education Service should organize sensitization workshops on manpower planning activities for officers of the Western Region Education Directorate once every year.
- b) The Centre for Educational Policy studies in UEW the Institute for Educational Planning and Administration at UCC in collaboration with the GES should hold annual training programmes for staff of the statistical units in the directorates.
- c) The various educational departments and school leaders in the directorates should greatly enhance the active participation of personnel in administration.
- d) The GES should regularly (biannually) organize leadership courses for heads of schools and educational units in the directorates.
- e) Conditions of service for educational workers should be improved by the GES.

References

- Ambekar, Y. (2004). *Manpower Planning* www.buzzle.com
- Anamuah-Mensah, J. (2002). "Fifteen Years of Education Reforms, The Way Forward" *Tertiary Education Series*. Accra: National Council for Tertiary Education
- Boateng, D. O. (2007). "Academic Excellence and Human Resource Development" *Daily Graphic* (No. 15009) p.11.
- Conyers, D. (1982). *An Introduction to Social Planning in the Third World*. New York: John Wiley and sons Publisher
- Daft, R. L. (1995). *Organizational Theory and Design*. Fifth Edition. Minneapolis: Yale University Press
- Gay, T. (1986). *Methodology of Educational Research*. Dehli: Vikas Publisher
- Graham, C. K. (2005). *The History of education in Ghana*. Accra Ghana Publishing Corporation
- Harbison, E. M. (1973). *Educational administration and Organizational behaviour*. Boston: Allyn and Bacon
- Hartman, W. T. (1988). *School District Budgeting*. Englewood-Cliff: Prentice Hall Inc.

- Mankoe, J. O. (2007). *Educational Administration and Management in Ghana*. Kumasi: Payless Publication.
- Ministry of Education MOE (1995). *Manpower Challenges in Education*. Accra: MOE
- Nti, J. (1975). Ghana's Experience at Administrative Reforms of the Central Bureaucracy. *Greenhill Journal of Administration* 2 (2), 34-39.
- Nyarko, J.K. (1991). "The Role of Local Government in Rural Development" *Local Government Information Digest*. 4(1), 49-56.
- Owens, R. G. (1987). *Organizational Behaviour in Education*. Englewood Cliffs: Prentice-Hall Inc.
- Okulo-Epak, Y. (1985). *District Development Planning Management*. Accra: Ministry of Finance and Economic Planning.
- Oyedeeji, N. B. (2006). Manpower Planning in Education: The Role of the Educational Administrator. *Ghana Journal of Education and Teaching*. 1(4), 91-97.
- Rebore, R. W. (1987). *Personnel Administration in Education: A Management Approach*. New York: Random House.
- Sergiovanni, T. J. (1996). *Supervision: Human Perspective*. New York: McGraw-Hill Book Company.
- Wiles, J. and Bondi, J. (2006). *Supervision: A Guide to Practice*. Columbus: Merrill Publishing Company.

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